

ASSESSMENT OF KNOWLEDGE OF DAIRY FARMERS REGARDING ZOOONOTIC DISEASES IN INDORE DISTRICT

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Abstract

The study was conducted to assess the knowledge level of dairy farmers regarding zoonotic diseases in Indore district of Madhya Pradesh. Data were collected through face to face structured schedule by randomly selected 150 dairy farmers from two tehsil of Indore district i.e Mhow and Rau. Knowledge index was calculated to find out the level of knowledge of dairy farmers regarding zoonotic diseases. Results revealed that only 23.33 per cent of dairy farmers were aware about possibility of diseases transmit either animal to human being and human being to animal. About half (49.33%) of respondents knew that disposal of carcasses in an open area can spread diseases in the surrounding environment. It was also observed that rabies were identified as zoonotic disease by majority of dairy farmers (98.67 %) followed by dermatitis/ scabies (59.33%), brucellosis (18.00%). As far as knowledge of dairy farmers about route of transmission it was observed that majority of the respondent knew about disease transmission through bite of arthropods/ insect bite (71.33%) followed by inhalation route (22.67 %). Majority of dairy farmers (54.67%) knew that tuberculosis can transmit from human to human only. However, 36.67 per cent farmers had knowledge that consumption of raw milk poses risk of tuberculosis in human being. Knowledge index (KI %) of dairy farmers regarding rabies was 64.33 per cent, brucellosis 12.04 per cent and regarding tuberculosis was 38.97 percent. Majority of the dairy farmers (58.00%) had low level of knowledge about zoonotic diseases It is a major concern and extension agency should organize more awareness programme regarding zoonotic disease in this area to update the knowledge of dairy farmers.

Keywords: Zoonotic Diseases, Knowledge and Dairy Farmers

Introduction

According to 19th livestock census Madhya Pradesh has 535.78 million livestock population (Census, 2019). In India, MP holds 6th rank in milk production. Dairy animal production is affected by a variety of common infectious illnesses (Shrama et al., 2015), majority of them are zoonotic in nature. Zoonotic illnesses are those diseases that are naturally transferred from vertebrates to humans and vice versa (WHO, 2015). In Indian culture, the farmers stay in close proximity with the animals. Zoonotic diseases continue to be important threats to human health across the world (Tebug, 2013).

A variety of factors contribute to the risk of zoonotic illness. Increased contact between animal and human, similar to the animals' enhanced raising method, continues to play an important role in their emergence and persistence (Tebug, 2013). So in present scenario one health approach is need of hour. one health approach recognizes that animal health, human health and environment are inextricably connected.

Lack of awareness among livestock owners is one of the important factors in the spread of diseases and it is also a major hurdle in controlling zoonotic diseases (Asokan et al., 2011). To Control of zoonotic diseases first priority is seeking knowledge how to deal with the zoonoses. This knowledge is the input of a control strategy (Boekhorst et al., 2010). Considering to all above facts, the present study was carried out to study the knowledge level of dairy farmers regarding zoonotic diseases in Indore District of M.P..

Methodology

The study was carried out in Indore district of Madhya Pradesh. Two tehsils Mhow and Rau has been selected for the proposed study. Two villages from each selected tehsil and 25 dairy farmers from each selected villages, were taken for the study making a total sample of 150 dairy farmers possessing at least 1-2 dairy animals.

The data were collected by personal interview schedule from randomly selected dairy farmers. Interview schedule contain various questions to test the knowledge level of respondents. The responses will be obtained on a graded scale. i.e., correct, near to correct, wrong or do not know response. Maximum scores were given to correct answer and decreasing order were assigned to nearly correct and zero to wrong and do not know answer. Level of knowledge of dairy farmers was calculated through following formula

$$KI = \frac{\text{Score obtained by respondent}}{\text{Maximum obtainable score}} \times 100$$

Respondents were categorized into three groups based on the mean and standard deviation of knowledge inde

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S. No.	Knowledge Category	Score
1	Low	<Mean- S.D.
2	Medium	Mean ± S.D.
3	High	>Mean + S.D.

Results and Discussion

Knowledge Level of Dairy Farmers Regarding Zoonotic Diseases.

Knowledge is the body of understood information possessed by dairy farmers about zoonotic diseases. knowledge level of dairy farmers regarding zoonotic diseases were studied on different aspects i.e. awareness about zoonotic diseases- transmission, name of important zoonotic diseases, awareness about possible risk of spread of zoonotic diseases and detailed knowledge about Rabies, Brucellosis and Tuberculosis. Findings are presented in table 01 and 02.

Knowledge of Dairy Farmers About General Awareness Regarding Zoonotic Diseases

It was observed that 16.67 per cent of the dairy farmers had knowledge about possibility to transmit diseases from cattle/buffalo to human being while only 6.67 per cent of the dairy farmers knew that about diseases can be transmit from human being to cattle/buffalo also. It was also evident that only 23.33 per cent of dairy farmers were aware about possibility of diseases transmit either animal to human being and human being to animal. It means 76.67 per cent of them were unaware about this (Table 01). Overall knowledge index (KI%) of dairy farmers regarding general awareness of zoonotic diseases is 11.67 per cent. Similarly Chinchwadkar and Panda (2020) observed that 75.00 per cent of farm women did not have knowledge about zoonotic diseases transferred from animal to human being.

Knowledge About Transmission Routes of Zoonotic Diseases

Findings suggested that about 46 per cent of the dairy farmers had knowledge about possibility of disease transmission by direct or indirect contact with animals and 76.67 per cent of respondents also knows that consumption of contaminated milk and water can transmit zoonotic diseases to human being. Only 22.67 per cent of the respondent had knowledge about inhalation route of transmission of zoonotic diseases. Majority of the respondents (71.33 %) awared about spread of zoonotic diseases through arthropods/ insect bite and poor hygienic practices (74.67%) (Table 01). Overall knowledge index (KI%) of dairy farmers regarding knowledge about transmission routes of zoonotic diseases is 58.26 per cent. Present finding had substantial support from the finding of

Sarita et al. (2017) who reported that 29.60 per cent and 33.60 per cent of dairy farmers were aware of zoonoses transmission through animals and milk, respectively.

Awareness About Risk of Zoonotic Diseases

Perusal of table 01 revealed that 49.33 per cent of respondents known about the fact that disposal of carcasses in an open area can spread diseases in the surrounding environment. Further only 20.66 per cent of respondents had knowledge about assisting animals during parturition with bare hands expose them to infectious diseases. Knowledge index (KI%) regarding knowledge about possible risk of diseases source was calculated as 35.00 per cent. Similar finding were observed by Rajkumar *et al.* (2016) that only 16.40 per cent respondents knew that the diseases can transmitted from animal to human beings.

Knowledge of Dairy Farmers About Name of Important Zoonotic Diseases

When dairy farmers were asked about name of zoonotic disease, 98.67 per cent dairy farmers knew about rabies followed by dermatitis/ scabies (59.33%) and brucellosis (18.00%). Further is was also observed that only 6.00 per cent and 4.00 per cent of farmers knew that foot-mouth diseases and bovine tuberculosis were zoonotic respectively. Overall knowledge index (KI%) of dairy farmers regarding knowledge about name of important zoonotic disease is 37.20 per cent. Present finding had substantial agreement with finding reported by Babu et al. (2015) who observed hat respondent were aware about rabies (100%). Similarly Rajkumar et al. (2016) reported that only very few 4.80 percent knew about zoonotic potential of brucellosis followed by 3.06 per cent, 6.80 per cent and 22.40 per cent of respondents knew about tuberculosis, anthrax, avian flu respectively. However Pandey (2013) reported that farmers were aware about zoonotic nature of rabies (81.67%), followed by T.B. (69.17%), Japanese Encephalitis(35.83%), Brucellosis (12.50%), parasitic diseases (01.67%).

Table 01: Distribution of the respondents according to knowledge about different parameters regarding zoonotic diseases (n=150)

S. No.	Knowledge parameters	No. of farmers (n)	Per cent (%)	Knowledge Index (%)
1	General awareness regarding zoonotic diseases			
	Possibility of disease transmission from cattle/buffalo to human being	25	16.67	11.67
	Possibility of disease transmission from human being to cattle/buffalo	10	06.67	
2	Knowledge about diseases transmission*			
	Consumption of contaminated milk and water	115	76.67	

	Inhalation route	34	22.67	58.26
	Bite of arthropods/ insect bite	107	71.33	
	Poor hygienic practices	112	74.67	
3	Awareness about possibility risk of diseases spread			
	Disposal of carcasses in an open area can spread diseases	74	49.33	35.00
	Assisting animals with bare hands during parturition can transmit diseases	31	20.66	
4	Name of important zoonotic diseases*			
	Rabies	148	98.67	37.20
	Brucellosis	27	18.00	
	Bovine tuberculosis	06	04.00	
	Foot mouth disease	09	06.00	
	Dermatitis / scabies	89	59.33	

*Multiple response.

Knowledge of Dairy Farmers Regarding Rabies

Perusal of table 02 revealed that about 98.00 per cent of the dairy farmers had knowledge about rabies disease transmission from animal to human and 96.67 per cent of the respondents knew that bite of rabid dog/cat can transmit of rabies. Further 50.00 per cent and 12.67 per cent of respondents had knowledge about contact with saliva of rabid dog and blood oozing/ scratch by rabid dog/cat are the possible transmission routes for rabies, respectively. Overall knowledge index (KI %) of dairy farmers regarding rabies is 64.33 per cent.

Knowledge of Dairy Farmers Regarding Brucellosis

Findings suggested that 21.33 per cent respondents knew about the transmission of zoonoses by direct contact or artificial insemination while 46.00 per cent knew the transmission of brucellosis by infected bull to the whole herd. Only 13.33 per cent of respondents possessed knowledge that brucellosis can be transmitted by consumption of raw milk. Only 18.00 per cent of respondents knew that various species of animals are susceptible for brucellosis. Very few respondents had knowledge about the symptoms of brucellosis in animals (13.34%) and brucellosis can cause abortion in animals in last trimester (19.33%). Only 22.00 per cent of respondents knew that symptoms brucellosis in human beings. None of the respondents knew about that routine field test for diagnosis of brucellosis in animals. Further it was observed only 18.00 per cent of respondents had knowledge about the vaccination facility available against the brucellosis. Overall knowledge index (KI%) of dairy farmers regarding brucellosis is 12.04 per cent. It was very amazed to note that though brucellosis known by only few respondents (18.00%), but understanding regarding certain aspects of brucellosis was more than that. Similar finding reported by Sharma *et al.* (2015) who revealed that only 22.60% of farmers were aware of the brucellosis illness and had little knowledge of the disease's zoonotic element and mode of

transmission.

Knowledge of Dairy Farmers Regarding Tuberculosis

Findings presented in table 02 revealed that majority of respondents (54.67%) knew about transmission of tuberculosis from human being to human being. Further 7.34 per cent respondents knew about the transmission of T.B. from infected animal to animals and infected human being to animals and vice versa (3.33%). it was also observed that 24.67 per cent dairy farmers knew about indirect contact/inhalation can cause tuberculosis and it can also be transmitted through milk (30.67 %).

Data further revealed that 58.67 per cent of respondents had knowledge about symptoms of tuberculosis in human and only 9.33 per cent respondents knew about symptoms of tuberculosis in animals. About 46.67 per cent of respondents opined that tuberculosis is curable by complete treatment. As far as knowledge about routine field test for diagnosis of tuberculosis in animals, it was observed that majority of respondents (90.67%) didn't know about routine field test available for diagnosis of tuberculosis in animals. About 34.00 per cent of respondents had knowledge regarding vaccination against tuberculosis. Data further revealed that knowledge about suitable practices for prevention of tuberculosis in human being were using the cooked animal product (20.00%) and separating house of human from animal shed (81.33%). It was also found that 86.00 per cent, 18.00 per cent, 70.67 per cent, 44.67 per cent and 16.00 per cent of respondents knew that covering mouth and nose/use mask, vaccination, isolating the patients, avoid sharing utensils and early treatment of patients were suitable practices to reduce transmission of tuberculosis in human to human respectively. It was observed that though tuberculosis as zoonotic disease was known by 4.00 per cent of farmers, but certain aspects related to tuberculosis were known by more than 04.00 per cent of the farmers. Overall knowledge index (KI%) of dairy farmers regarding tuberculosis is 38.97 per cent. Similar findings were reported by Addo (2011).

Table 02: Distribution of the Respondents According To Their Brief Knowledge About Important Zoonotic Diseases (n=150)

S. No.	Knowledge Parameters*	Category	No. of farmers (n)	Per cent (%)	Knowledge index (KI%)
1	Brief Knowledge About Rabies				
	Possibility to transmit rabies disease from Animal to human		147	98.00	64.33
	Rabies can be caused by bite of rabid dog/cat		145	96.67	
	Rabies can be caused by saliva of rabid dog		75	50	
	Rabies can be caused by blood oozing / scratch by rabid		19	12.67	

	dog/cat				
2	Brief Knowledge About Brucellosis				
	Knowledge about transmission through direct contact or artificial insemination		32	21.33	12.04
	Knowledge about transmission through Infected bull		69	46.00	
	Transmission of brucellosis in human being through consumption of raw milk		20	13.33	
	Knowledge about susceptible Species for Brucellosis		27	18.00	
	Symptoms of Brucellosis in animals		20	13.33	
	Knowledge about abortion in particular trimester of animal's gestation period		29	19.33	
	Symptoms of Brucellosis in human being		33	22.00	
	Knowledge about routine field test for diagnosis of Brucella		00	00.00	
	Knowledge about vaccine against Brucellosis		27	18.00	
3	Brief Knowledge About Tuberculosis				

	Knowledge about transmission of T.B.*	Infected Human to human	82	54.67	P
		Infected Animal to animal	11	07.34	
		Infected human to bovine and as well as bovine to human	05	03.33	
		Indirect contact contaminated/ inhalation of droplet	37	24.67	
		Consumption of raw milk	46	30.67	
	Knowledge about the Symptoms of T.B in human being *		88	58.67	38.97

	Know about the Symptoms of tuberculosis in animal		14	09.33
	Tuberculosis is curable in animals	Yes	70	46.67
		No	31	20.67
		Don't know	49	32.67
	Knowledge about routine field test for diagnosis of tuberculosis in animal	Yes	14	09.33
		No	136	90.67
	Suitable practices for prevention of tuberculosis in human *	Using the cooked animal product (milk and meat)	30	20.00
		Separating house of human from animal shed	122	81.33
	Suitable methods practices for reduce transmission of tuberculosis in human being *	Covering mouth and nose/ use mask	129	86.00
		Vaccination	27	18.00
		Isolating the patients	106	70.67
		Avoid sharing utensils	67	44.67
		Early treatment of patients	24	16.00

*Multiple response

Overall Knowledge of Dairy Farmers Regarding Zoonotic Diseases

It is observed from table 03 that slightly more than half of the dairy farmers (58.00%) had low level of knowledge about zoonotic diseases followed by medium level (27.33%) and high level of knowledge (14.67%) respectively. Hundal et al. (2016) were also reported that majority of respondents (69.20%) belong to low to medium knowledge level categories, whereas 30.80 percent of respondents had high knowledge about zoonotic diseases.

Table 03: Distribution of the respondents according to overall knowledge level regarding zoonotic diseases (n=150)

S.No.	Knowledge level	No. of farmers (n)	Per cent (%)
1.	Low (KI < 32.0)	87	58.00
2.	Medium (KI 32.1 to 42.5)	41	27.33
3.	High (KI > 42.5)	22	14.67

Figure 01: Distribution of respondents according to overall knowledge level regarding zoonotic diseases

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it can be concluded that a significant majority of dairy farmers possess a limited understanding of zoonotic diseases. This lack of awareness is evident from the fact that a large proportion of the respondents did not have sufficient knowledge about these diseases, which poses a substantial public health concern. Zoonotic diseases, which can be transmitted from animals to humans, are critical to address in order to prevent outbreaks and ensure the well-being of both animals and people.

Given the current situation, it is crucial for extension agencies to take proactive measures to bridge this knowledge gap. Organizing comprehensive awareness programs and educational workshops is essential to enhance the dairy farmers' understanding of zoonotic diseases. Such initiatives should focus on providing practical information about the prevention, identification, and management of these diseases. By improving the knowledge base of dairy farmers, these programs can contribute significantly to better disease management practices, ultimately safeguarding both human and animal health in the region.

Furthermore, these awareness efforts should be continuous and tailored to address the specific needs and challenges faced by dairy farmers. Collaboration with veterinary experts and health professionals can ensure that the information disseminated is accurate and relevant. Overall, increased awareness and education are vital steps towards mitigating the risks associated with zoonotic diseases and promoting a healthier and more informed farming community.

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